

germination even at 20 ppm Zn. Values for vigor, which is considered a reliable index of seed potency, indicated that all the varieties performed best at 5 ppm Zn. Higher concentrations (15 and 20

ppm) reduced Jaya and IR20 vigor, but not that of Kanchi (see table). EC of the seed leachates after soaking in Zn was negatively correlated with

germination and seedling vigor. Zn had little effect on endosperm weight, but germination percentage was closely related to seed treatment. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Ratoon regeneration in rices and their single-cross hybrids after three cuttings

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Sixteen single-cross hybrids of 15 rice varieties were planted in Aug 1982 at Main Research Station, Bangalore. F2 seeds were harvested on 24 Jan, 20 Aug, and 10 Dec 1983. After the third ratooning, stubble was left in situ or transplanted in single rows containing 30 slips. Thirty-five days after cutting and transplanting, plant height and number of tillers per plant were recorded (see table). Plant height was measured from the ground to the tip of the topmost leaf.

Hybrids had greater regeneration capacity than varieties. Hybrid TNI/Type 3 had the best regeneration ability. Among varieties, Type 3 had good regeneration. Many varieties could not be propagated in situ after the third cutting. Vegetative propagation of

Plant height and tillers per plant on 20 plants 35 d after thud cutting.

	Plant height (cm)		Tillers (no.)	
	In situ	Transplanted	In situ	Transplanted
<i>Cross</i>				
TNI/Type 3	56.2±3.6	67.4±1.7	24.7±4.0	14.8±4.7
Jaya/Type 3	54.9±1.9	53.0±1.4	31.9±5.5	7.2±0.4
PK150/Basumathi	54.5±3.6	21.0±3.5	31.1±4.1	2.0±0.4
Mashuri/Doddi	51.1±1.4	45.9±2.5	19.1±3.1	3.6±0.4
Mashuri/Prakash	46.9±1.9	39.8±2.3	22.2±3.7	5.4±0.5
IET7031/Telahamsa	44.1±1.8	35.1±2.6	20.4±2.9	1.9±0.5
SHM 1/Intan Mutant 1	44.2±1.7	32.8±8.6	7.1±1.4	3.3±0.5
Type 3/Telahamsa	44.3±1.8	47.0±1.5	22.8±1.6	10.5±0.7
TNI/Telahamsa	39.4±1.4	30.1±1.5	18.3±2.2	3.8±0.7
Jaya/Telahamsa	35.6±2.1	30.5±4.2	12.3±1.5	2.6±0.5
Jaya/Mashuri	38.5±1.3	34.3±1.7	20.3±2.7	4.8±0.5
Jaya/IET7031	38.4±2.3	32.3±2.4	16.0±1.1	2.5±0.5
PK150/IR36	37.9±2.6	28.2±1.9	18.2±1.9	4.4±0.6
Mangla/Telahamsa	37.1±0.9	33.4±1.6	19.0±3.2	3.0±0.4
PK177/Intan Mutant 1	36.8±1.5	34.6±1.3	14.2±1.5	5.1±0.6
IET7031/Mangla	36.4±4.3	30.6±2.9	6.6±3.9	3.1±0.6
<i>Variety</i>				
Type 3	52.3±3.9	53.9±2.1	14.8±2.6	3.8±0.4
Jaya	29.8±3.5	31.7±2.1	7.7±0.9	3.2±0.4
Mangla	36.7±2.9	34.3±1.9	3.7±2.2	4.2±0.3
Telahamsa	37.4±0.9	27.2±1.6	15.3±3.1	2.5±0.3
Mashuri	42.4±2.2	36.4±1.6	—	4.3±0.4
TNI	—	29.1±1.9	—	4.1±0.5
Prakash	—	34.3±2.1	—	4.7±0.4
Intan Mutant 1	—	45.3±2.6	—	4.7±0.7
Doddi	—	50.6±1.5	—	3.9±0.7

single-cross hybrids allows continuous production of F2 seeds and maximizes

the population size of the second segregating generation of any cross. *S*

Performance of male-sterile and maintainer lines and crosses

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We evaluated Chinese cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A and corresponding maintainers V20B and Zhen Shan 97B in 1983 wet and 1984 dry season at CLDRRI. In wet season, they matured early and had low phenotypic acceptability (scale 5),

Table 1. Agronomic traits of cms lines and maintainers at O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>1983 wet season</i>							
V20A	89	75	304				
V20B	91	67	274	74	38	29	2.9
Zhen Shan 97A	93	73	218				
Zhen Shan 97B	97	69	212	137	27	27	2.2
<i>1984 dry season</i>							
V20A	90	71	363				
V20B	97	71	284	74	16	30	2.3
Zhen Shan 97A	93	68	297				
Zhen Shan 97B	103	74	269	97	26	28	2.8

Table 2. Seed set on cms lines due to cross-pollination with maintainers and elite lines, O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Cross	Seed set (%) on cms lines
<i>1983 wet season</i>	
V20A/V20B	4
Zhen Shan 97A/Zhen Shan 91B	2
V20A/NN3A (IR36)	10
V20A/NN4B (IR42)	3
V20A/IR54	2
97A/NN3A	9
97A/NN4B	2
97A/IR54	4
<i>1984 dry season</i>	
V20A/V20B	43
Zhen Shan 97 A/Zhen Shan 97B	36
V20A/NN3A	21
V20A/NN6A (IR2307.247.2.2.3)	30
V20A/IR56	32
V20A/OM33 (IR9224.73.2.2.2.3)	26
V20A/IR8423.132.6.2.2	34
V20A/NN7A (IR9129.192.2.3.5)	35
97A/NN3 A	35
97A/NN6A	33
97A/IR56	41
97A/OM33	26
97A/IR8423	35
97A/NN7 A	40

less panicles/m², and high sterility (Table 1). The maintainers had high 1,000-grain weight. V20B and Zhen Shan 97B yielded less than 3 t/ha in both seasons. The lines were resistant to blast but highly susceptible to stem borer and sheath rot. Panicles of cms plants often showed incomplete exertion.

Outcrossing pollination between cms lines, maintainers, and some elite lines was evaluated in the greenhouse in 1983 wet season and in the field in 1984 dry season. Female-to-male ratio was 4:1. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Maintainers were sown 5 d later than cms lines and sowing time of elite lines was adjusted to synchronize flowering. Ropes were pulled across plots to encourage cross-pollination, but we did not clip leaves or apply gibberellic acid to improve panicle exertion.

Filled and unfilled grains were counted on 20 plants of each cms line. Cross pollination was 2-10% in wet season and 21-43% in dry season (Table 2). *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Phylogenetic mutation for grain type in japonica rice after mutagen treatment of fertilized egg cells

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Fertilized egg cells of japonica Taichung 65 were treated with 0.5 or 1.0 mM N-methyl N-nitrosourea (MNU) 12 h after anthesis by panicle dipping method for 1, 2, and 3 h. Each treatment had 500 fertilized egg cells. Seeds from treated panicles were harvested 40 d after treatment and the M₁ was planted in the field.

Mutants with indica grain type (length:breadth >2.0) are shown in Table 1, and grain characters of some mutants are in Table 2. Length:breadth of grains of indica mutants was 2.71 to 3.47, compared to the parent ratio of 1.72.

Different grain types of mutants. 1 = parent, 2 = long grain, 3 = awned spikelets.

Table 1. Frequency of progenies with indica grain type in M₁ population.

MNU treatment	M ₁ plants (no.) tested	M ₁ plants (no.) with indica grain type	Frequency (%)
Control (water)	200	0	0.000
0.5 mM for 1 h	510	0	0.000
2 h	1261	9	0.714
3 h	577	2	0.347
1.0 mM for 1 h	540	4	0.740
2 h	881	11	1.248
3 h	512	3	0.586

Table 2. Grain characters of indica mutants in M₁.

Mutant line	Grain size (mm) (length × breadth)	Length:breadth	100-grain weight (g)
T3 - 995	7.01 × 2.25	3.11	2.0
T4 - 1462	7.14 × 2.06	3.47	2.2
T5 - 2020	6.23 × 2.27	2.74	2.0
T5 - 2123	6.29 × 2.28	2.76	2.1
T6 - 2282	7.20 × 2.12	3.40	2.2
T6 - 2284	6.96 × 2.08	3.35	2.0
T6 - 2396	2.96 × 2.04	3.41	2.1
T6 - 2423	6.13 × 2.26	2.71	2.0
T7 - 2974	6.33 × 2.29	2.77	2.1
T7 - 2918	5.64 × 2.03	2.78	1.6
Parent	5.00 × 2.91	1.72	2.4